

Hybrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency by Integration of Dc Equipment

Work Package WP3

Hybrid grid enabling solutions (automation, technologies, components and validation)

Deliverable D3.5

Microgrid MV DC CB ICT

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List of Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
ADU	Application Data Unit
ARP	Address Resolution Protocol
CB	Circuit Breaker
DC	Direct Current
IED	Intelligent Electronic Device
IP	Internet Protocol
LSB	Least Significant Bit
MVDC	Medium Voltage Direct Current
RCS	Residual Current Switch
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
VI	Vacuum Interrupter
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Deliverable D3.5 is a report on the work done to adapt the circuit breaker controller to enable the exchange of information between Medium Voltage Direct Current (MVDC) circuit breakers and the control computer of the target grid of the breakers.

The document details the requirements on the speed of communication. It also briefly describes how the chosen method of communication, the MODBUS protocol, is to be used in this part of the HYPERRIDE project.

The report presents tests of the implemented communication stack with the help of a test environment developed to emulate the client of the communication in the target grid.

The document furthermore outlines what the efforts should be focused on in the near future regarding the communication interfacing in order to achieve goals of the HYPERRIDE project.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

The purpose of Task 3.5 is to develop suitable software that enable the communication between the MVDC Circuit Breaker (CB) built as part of Work Package (WP) 3 of the HYPERRIDE project and the converter control computer that is used in the German demonstrator site of the same project.

The document reports on the development of the communication software and firmware, detailing the software specifications and presenting initial tests.

As the deliverable report is due to be submitted before the installation of the MVDC CB, actual on-site communication tests cannot be included in this document. However, a suitable test environment has been developed as part of the effort in order to make sure that upon delivery, the circuit breaker can be successfully integrated into the protection system with the least amount of interfacing and communication issues possible.

1.2 Structure of the Document

The structure of the report is outlined below.

Section 2 gives an overview of the part of the target grid that is relevant for this deliverable as well as a short description of the MVDC CB. Section 3 describes the structure of the implemented MODBUS application and of the UDP/IP communication stack. Section 4 presents initial test results and Section 5 concludes the report.

2 Background

The goal of this deliverable is to report the effort invested in creating a communication platform that enables the exchange of information between Scibreak's MVDC circuit breakers and the control computer of the Aachen demo site.

2.1 Overview of the Aachen demo site

The Aachen demo site is a test grid located on the campus of RWTH in Aachen, Germany. It is one of the three demonstration sites that are utilized in the HYPERRIDE project. The following paragraphs give an overview of the grid in order to provide the context of this report.

The grid is fed from the Alternating Current (AC) utility network by means of AC/Direct Current (DC) as well as DC/DC converters (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Circuit diagram of the Aachen demo site.

The MVDC part of the grid has a symmetric monopolar configuration, with its midpoint connected to ground via high impedance. The grid is under development and constant upgrading, but at the time of writing this report (early 2023), the network consists of power electronics converters, cables, fuses as well as disconnectors.

The power electronics converters are central equipment of the test grid. How their design influences the magnitude and rate of rise of fault currents and which requirements this poses for the MVDC CB are covered in Section 6 of an earlier report of WP 3 of the HYPERRIDE project (Norrgra et al., 2022).

The converters are autonomous in the sense that they can operate in a safe manner by themselves, without the need of a higher-level control mechanism. However, as the optimal power flow of a grid is a global state of the network, it cannot be achieved without a higher-level control that oversees the individual power converters and can issue different setpoints of operation to different converters. This higher-level controller would be implemented on a computer in case of the FEN Research Grid (Figure 2).

The layout of the grid has an impact on how the optimal power flow can be achieved, therefore the higher-level control computer needs to be informed about the grid topology. When a circuit

Figure 2: Control computer of the MVDC part of the Aachen demo site.

breaker operates, this usually causes the network topology to change, so it is beneficial from the grid operation point of view if the circuit breaker can communicate with the control computer and can inform it about such changes.

2.2 Use of communication between controller and breaker

As part of the HYPERRIDE project, Scibreak have to deploy two MVDC circuit breakers in the Aachen demo site. These circuit breakers are designed to interrupt line currents associated with both normal operation as well as fault scenarios. A characteristic trait of DC systems is quickly rising fault currents when compared to those occurring in AC systems. Therefore, DC circuit breakers need quick fault detection, decision making and current interruption. The requirement for speed is quite stringent; the targeted length of the fault neutralization time (see Figure 3) is 1–1.5 ms. The breaker operating time is in the range of 0.8–1.2 ms, which leaves only around 0.5 ms delay for the fault detection and communication delay to the breaker. This type of reaction speed is only necessary for handling extreme fault cases, but nevertheless those cases lead to requirements on maximum communication latency.

The standard family IEC 61850 (that includes the GOOSE protocol whose use in this project is detailed further at the end of this Section) is a possible choice to adhere to when designing communication platforms for industrial systems. As the protocols included in IEC 61850 are Ethernet-based, this poses a limitation on the expected largest communication speeds between parties of the communication method due to latency. The relevant standard version applicable at the time of writing this report is IEC 61850-5-2013 and this defines the transfer time to be not more than 3 ms for a 'Trip' signal. Therefore, it cannot be taken for granted that a trip command issued by a higher-order control device would always reach the circuit breaker faster

Figure 3: Definitions according to CIGRE working group A3/B4.34 TB 683.

than this.

The requirement for the fault neutralization time combined with that of the IEC 61850 standard family regarding the communication speed imply that the circuit breakers must be autonomous. The converter control computer cannot be actively involved in the operation of the MVDC circuit breakers when it comes to short-circuit protection. However, the computer could use the data collected by the sensors of the circuit breaker such as line currents through the breaker or voltage over the VI as help for monitoring the grid.

Moreover, for the purposes of grid topology changes, the computer could issue open/close orders which would result in the connection or disconnection of parts of the protected system. These orders would be interpreted by the breaker controller and different operations would be performed. In case of opening the breaker when small or no currents flow through the Vacuum Interrupter (VI), the Residual Current Switch (RCS) connected in series with the CB (and integrated into the circuit breaker cabinet, being a subsystem of the breaker) would be opened. In case of currents larger than the breaking capability of the RCS, the CB would open first, thereby performing current limitations and shortly afterwards would the RCS open. Ordering the breaker to close would technically mean that the open RCS is closed when the CB is closed and ready to interrupt the fault current that may result in a closing operation on a grid fault.

The state diagrams of the planned operation of the breakers is included in the Appendix of this report.

Possible means of communication for automation include MODBUS, Ethercat, Profinet and SERCOS, or subsets of IEC 61850 and IEC 60870 MMS. Since the breakers will detect faults and operate autonomously, there are no strict requirements on communication latency, that would otherwise result from the need for a fast trip signal. Since there is no strict need for low latency communication or for long messages, a relatively simple protocol such as MODBUS can be used. Moreover, the control computer of the FEN Research Grid communicates with other devices of the grid through MODBUS, so it lends itself to implement the communication between the circuit breakers and the computer in a similar way.

Another protocol could be used for communication, e.g., the implementation of GOOSE might prove to be sufficiently easy. But it is advantageous to use a single protocol for the whole grid, so in case other devices are already using something else, then implementing GOOSE for to be used by two devices only may not be justified.

3 Communication Interface

3.1 General

The goal of the communication is to obtain information stored in the breaker controller memory, to issue orders to the breaker and to convey information from the breaker to the external control device if the breaker initiates this.

It has been decided that the converter control computer and the circuit breaker should communicate with one another by an Ethernet-based method. The chosen protocol is MODBUS, which is a commonly used protocol in the communication of industrial devices. The implementation has been selected to be a User Datagram Protocol (UDP)/Internet Protocol (IP)-based stack.

As the means of the communication, MODBUS requests and corresponding responses are to be used to convey the information and the orders.

The circuit breaker has an interface Intelligent Electronic Device (IED) that manages the communication between the circuit breaker and the 'outside world'. This IED makes the connection of an Ethernet cable to the breaker possible, thus it enables Ethernet-based communication.

The interface IED runs a microcontroller that takes care of the communication with devices external to the breaker. The UDP/IP stack is implemented on this microcontroller. The converter control computer runs an operating system, so freely available IP stack implementations can be used. The MODBUS protocol as well as the MODBUS application (both client and server) were programmed by Scibreak for the breaker. In case of the control computer, RWTH programmed the MODBUS application.

In this document, 'client' refers to the control computer of the Aachen demo site and 'server' refers to the interface IED of the VARC circuit breaker. The only exception to this is the 'Breaker interface IED as the client of the communication' subsection of this section.

3.2 Information to exchange

A register in this document refers to a block of certain number of bytes that is available for the processor running on the interface IED for reading and storing data. A coil means a single, addressable bit for reading and storing information.

Table 1 gives an overview of the information that could be enquired from the server by the client.

The voltage and current can be stored as integer values on 2 bytes each. The presence of a breaker failure, the state of the breaker regarding being blocked/unblocked and being ready or not ready as well as its position (open or closed) can be stored as bits of a register. This means that data on the status of the breaker could be stored on 6 bytes in total: 2x2 bytes plus the status bits stored on 2 bytes (certain implementations may have 2-byte-long registers).

Once the request for any of this information is received, the interface IED can sample the sensors' output and store the data on a dedicated register.

The orders that can be sent to the breaker would be the ones listed in Table 2.

Table 1: Breaker status info and stored measurements.

Name of information	Size in bits	Comment
VI voltage	16	Measured voltage over the VI of the breaker
Line current	16	Measured current through the busbar of the breaker
Breaker status info (breaker open, breaker failure, breaker unblocked, breaker ready)	4	Information on the breaker status (bitwise: breaker is open, breaker failure detected, breaker is unblocked, breaker is ready to perform a current interruption)

The three orders that can be communicated by setting a single bit are 'open breaker', 'close breaker' and 'unlock breaker'. These could be stored in a single register, preferably as the Least Significant Bit (LSB) and adjacent bits. This implies that a 'write single register' MODBUS function may be better suited for conveying orders than the 'write single coil' function (see the 'MODBUS functions to be used' section).

Table 2: External orders.

Order	Size in registers/bits
Open/close breaker, unlock breaker	1/16
Set breaker trip level	1/16

3.3 Retransmitting packets

As UDP does not guarantee packet delivery and acknowledgement of reception, a policy regarding missing feedback during the communication process needs to be drafted.

The acknowledgment of a reception of a message which is a characteristic trait of the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) will be omitted. However, the MODBUS application running on the server (regardless of which device is acting as the server at a given moment) will try to send a reply with a function code that corresponds to that of the request.

A counter on the side of the client is proposed that counts how many attempts the client has made at sending a request or order without receiving feedback. Once this counter reaches a predefined value, the client sends a warning message to the operator that the setup needs to be inspected manually (looking for dangling ethernet cables or checking if the breaker still has power etc.) and the counter can be reset.

The frequency at which a request or order is resent could be one attempt in a second (or anything that seems acceptable).

The server will reply to requests, but it will not try to resend information in case the client did not receive the first packet. In case of orders, the server will send back a MODBUS response that formally corresponds to the order. E.g., if ordering the breaker open is set by writing a register, then a MODBUS response is sent back once the write operation is completed.

The client will need to wait for a sufficiently long time in between issuing orders with opposing meaning. If the breaker is to open, then the server will not accept a 'close breaker' order until the execution of the first order is completed. In such a case, the server needs to send an error or exception message back to the client as a reply to the second order.

The 'breaker busy' described in section 'Breaker interface IED as the client of the communication' could be used to inform the control computer that waiting is necessary before another order can be issued.

3.4 MODBUS UDP/IP

MODBUS TCP over an UDP/IP stack is agreed upon. The interface IED will scan incoming Ethernet packets and drop anything that is not using the MAC address of the IED as the destination. To make the debugging easier when commissioning the breaker setup, ICMP can be implemented on the server so the interface IED would respond to ping. No broadcast messages other than Address Resolution Protocol (ARP) requests will be considered. The reason is that a network of computers and other devices can be noisy by continually exchanging broadcast messages to discover other entities.

A single Ethernet packet should constitute the unit of information exchange. The number of bytes in a single packet necessary to carry the MODBUS message is estimated to be no more than 306. This upper limit is yielded by considering the longest Application Data Unit (ADU) that may occur when using MODBUS TCP (refer to (*MODBUS Application Protocol Specification V1.1b3*, 2012)).

Packets of this length should pose no problem to modern CPUs or to the communication protocol stack when transmitted; they are expected to be sent without fragmentation. Avoiding packet fragmentation is advantageous as the UDP/IP stack does not need to keep track of which packet fragments have been received and in which order they should be put to correctly reconstruct the original packet. This length is broken down to different levels of the stack: (ETH header 14 bytes + (IP header 20 bytes + (UDP header 8 bytes + (MODBUS ADU 260 bytes))) + ETH FCS 4 bytes) = 306 bytes.

3.5 MODBUS functions to be used

A MODBUS function is the description of what action the client of the communication requests to be performed by the server of the communication. The different actions are referenced by their unique identifiers that are termed MODBUS function codes.

The functions listed in Table 3 will be implemented on the interface IED of the circuit breakers (for a more detailed implementation guide, refer to (*MODBUS Application Protocol Specification V1.1b3*, 2012)).

To keep in line with the original Modicon addressing convention (*Modicon Modbus Protocol Reference Guide*, 1996), the block of addresses will be defined as valid MODBUS function addresses for the different functions as indicated in the second column of Table 3.

Table 3: MODBUS functions to be implemented.

Function code	Starting address (byte)	Quantity of registers	Comment
03 Read holding registers	0x9C41 (decimal 40001)	1 to 3 registers	status register, voltage over VI, line current (6 bytes in total, on 3 registers)
04 Read input registers	0x7531 (decimal 30001)	1 to 3 registers	status register, voltage over VI, line current (6 bytes in total, on 3 registers)
06 Write single register	0x9C42 (decimal 40002)	1 register	breaker open (LSB), breaker close, breaker unblock, set breaker trip level (4 bytes in total, on 2 registers)
16 Write multiple registers	0x9C42 (decimal 40002)	1 to 2 registers	breaker open (LSB), breaker close, breaker unblock, set breaker trip level (4 bytes in total, on 2 registers)

3.6 Breaker interface IED as the client of the communication

It is considered advantageous to have the breaker enabled to initiate the communication with the control computer. The breaker can report if it detected and interrupted fault currents.

In order to prevent communication errors occurring due to misinterpretation of packets transmitted in a bidirectional channel when the interface IED may behave as a server and a client, two ports are to be used on both the control computer and the interface IED. When the interface IED tries to report intercepted fault events or checks if the communication link between it and the control computer is up, it does so by writing a specific register of the control computer by using a port different from that of which it receives the orders on. If the control computer sends back an affirmative MODBUS response, then the interface IED is aware of the communication link being up or that the control computer got notified of the reported trip event.

When acting as the client of the communication, the device should use 502 as the UDP destination port of the sent packets. The UDP source port can be anything other than 502. This should be implemented for both the control computer and the interface IED.

While the breaker is in the 'transitory states' (see Figure 13), it also sends out a 'breaker busy' message by setting a certain register of the control computer. The point of this is that if the control computer tried to issue an order while the breaker is not ready, it would get back the 'SERVER_DEVICE_BUSY' exception code as the MODBUS response to the order. With the additional information conveyed by the 'breaker busy' register set by the interface IED as client, the computer will be able to determine why the IED is busy.

When the control computer acts as the server of the communication, the MODBUS responses it sends out corresponding to the orders coming from the interface IED will not be used by the IED. That is, even though the client tries to set the 'breaker busy' register, in case of a negative response, it will just carry on without retrying.

4 Testing

Parallel to the development of the stack to be used on the microprocessor implemented on the interface IED, a communication stack has been developed on a computer running Linux operating system. The goal of this effort was to have a test environment for the implemented MODBUS communication so that the behaviour of the interface IED can be verified to be correct before the whole breaker unit is installed in the FEN Research Grid.

The schematic drawing of the implemented testing procedure is displayed in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Schematic diagram of the setup testing the interface IED functionality as the server.¹

In the following, an example demonstrates how a single register of the interface IED can be written and read with the help of the programmed test environment.

First, the value of register at address 40002 is read. This is implemented by assembling a packet that contains the relevant MODBUS information set by the user (as illustrated in Figure 5) and by receiving and breaking down the packet that the interface IED sends back as a response (as shown in Figure 6).

The input of the data illustrated in Figure 5 is done by the program prompting the user to enter the destination port, the code of the MODBUS function to be performed, the starting address of the registers on the server (in case a whole block of registers were to be manipulated) and the number of the registers on which the function is to be performed. There are built-in checks at every step when user input is queried and if the input provided falls out of predefined ranges or its format is not compliant with what is expected, the program warns the user and asks again.

The extracted packet shown in Figure 6 reveals how a response packet is built up. The first twelve bytes decode the MAC addresses of the client and the server, respectively. The following two bytes describe the type of the Ethernet frame. Then twelve bytes set different attributes of what is called the IP header part of the packet. After these, eight bytes decode the IP addresses of the client and the server, still as part of the IP header. These are followed by eight bytes of the UDP header part. The last several bytes shown are part of the MODBUS ADU.

In Figure 6, the bytes in green encode the MODBUS function code, the number of bytes read and the two-byte-long value stored in the register that was read from, respectively.

As the second step, the 'write single register' function is performed on the register at address 40002 by passing the data to the packet builder code (as displayed in Figure 7). The packet sent back by the interface IED is the response, which is broken down according to Figure 8.

¹source of the computer picture: <https://pixabay.com/vectors/computer-desktop-workstation-office-158675/>

```

Launching the receive executable.
Socket opened.
You can exit the loop by typing 'exit'
Enter the destination UDP port!
502
Port number entered: 502
Enter the MODBUS function code!
3
MODBUS function code entered: 3
Enter the address of the start register for MODBUS function 3 in dec format!
40002
Start register address in hex: 0x9c42
Enter the number of registers to be read for MODBUS function 3 in dec format!
1
Number of registers to be read in hex: 0x1
All parameters have been set for MODBUS function 3.

```

Figure 5: User input for assembling a packet that implements the 'read holding registers' function.

```

Test packet extraction: e4 5f 1 53 12 42 0 a 35 3 2 18 0 45 0 0 27 1 97 40 0
40 11 b4 3a c0 a8 1 aa c0 a8 1 fa 1 f6 1 f6 0 13 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 5 ff 3 2 0 0 0 0
Modbus data bytes: 3 2 0 0 0

```

Figure 6: Extracted packet of the response to the performed 'read holding registers' function.

In Figure 8, the bytes in the green box encode the MODBUS function code, the 2-byte-long address of the register to write to and the 2-byte-long new value to be written to the register, respectively.

```

Launching the receive executable.
Socket opened.
You can exit the loop by typing 'exit'
Enter the destination UDP port!
502
Port number entered: 502
Enter the MODBUS function code!
6
MODBUS function code entered: 6
Enter the address of the register for MODBUS function 6 in dec format!
40002
Start register address in hex: 0x9c42
Enter the number that is to be copied to the register for MODBUS function 6 in dec format!
426
The new content to be copied to the register in hex: 0x1aa
All parameters have been set for MODBUS function 6.

```

Figure 7: User input for assembling a packet that implements the 'write single register' function.

As the last step of the demonstration, a new 'read holding registers' function is implemented to read the same register at address 40002 to check if the value set by the previous step is available for fetching. The packet is assembled based on user input (as shown in Figure 9) and

```

Test packet extraction: e4 5f 1 53 12 42 0 a 35 3 2 1 8 0 45 0 0 28 1 9d 40 0
40 11 b4 33 c0 a8 1 aa c0 a8 1 fa 1 f6 1 f6 0 14 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 6 ff 6 9c 42 1 aa 0
Modbus data bytes: 6 9c 42 1 aa
  
```

Figure 8: Extracted packet of the response to the performed 'write single register' function.

the response is once again broken down as in Figure 10.

In Figure 10, the bytes in green encode the MODBUS function code, the number of bytes read and the now newly written, two-byte-long value stored in the register that was read from, respectively.

```

Launching the receive executable.
Socket opened.
You can exit the loop by typing 'exit'
Enter the destination UDP port!
502
Port number entered: 502
Enter the MODBUS function code!
3
MODBUS function code entered: 3
Enter the address of the start register for MODBUS function 3 in dec format!
40002
Start register address in hex: 0x9c42
Enter the number of registers to be read for MODBUS function 3 in dec format!
1
Number of registers to be read in hex: 0x1
All parameters have been set for MODBUS function 3.
  
```

Figure 9: Input for assembling another packet that implements the 'read holding registers' function.

```

Test packet extraction: e4 5f 1 53 12 42 0 a 35 3 2 1 8 0 45 0 0 27 1 a1 40 0
40 11 b4 30 c0 a8 1 aa c0 a8 1 fa 1 f6 1 f6 0 13 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 5 ff 3 2 1 aa 0 0
Modbus data bytes: 3 2 1 aa 0
  
```

Figure 10: Extracted packet of the response to the second 'read holding registers' function performed.

To complete the verification of the correct behaviour of the communication interface, all implemented MODBUS functions have to be checked. As the method of testing is practically the same for all the functions, further test results are not repeated in this report.

The interface IED acting as the client of the communication also needs to be verified, and the test method demonstrated in this Section can be used with minor modifications.

5 Conclusions

This report describes the how the communication protocol necessary for the integration of the MVDC circuit breakers in the frame of the HYPERRIDE project is developed. Section 2 provides a brief context description regarding the target grid of the breakers and how this impacts the communication protocol design (namely, scope and speed). Section 3 details how MODBUS will be used as the chosen protocol of communication and Section 4 presents evidence of the interface IED correctly functioning as the server of the communication.

As for further work related to this Task, all the implementations of the MODBUS functions to be used in this project need to be cross-checked and validated. Moreover, during the deployment of the circuit breakers to the Aachen demo site, it is expected that the fine-tuning of the communication system will be necessary.

References

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Appendix

State diagrams

Figure 11: State diagram of the breaker.

be used as an addition to Figure 11.

Status bits:

first: 0 - main breaker fault not detected, 1 - main breaker fault detected

second: 0 - main breaker unblocked, 1 - main breaker unblocked

third: 0 - main breaker not ready, 1 - main breaker ready

fourth: 0 - RCS closed, 1 - RCS open

'automatic "close main breaker"': the breaker is automatically guided to a state where it can stay in the closed position

'breaker trip': if the breaker is ready and detects a fault current through the VI, it automatically trips - this can also happen if the RCS is closed on a grid fault

'1: H': 'unlock breaker' order

'1: L': 'block breaker' order

'2: H': 'open breaker' order

'3: H': 'close breaker' order

'transitory states:': the breaker is not taking external orders

Note: it is not indicated for the cleaner appearance of the flowchart, but the transition from one state to another one can take approximately this much time:

Reception and processing of an order: few milliseconds

Capacitor charging: depending on the amount of charge needed, several seconds to several tens of seconds

Capacitor discharging: several seconds

RCS opening or closing time: several tens of milliseconds

Main breaker opening or closing time: few milliseconds

Additional notes to Figure 13

The state diagram had to be adjusted so that it would fit on the page. As part of the adjustment, explanatory text has been removed from the image. This text is included here instead and is to be used as an addition to Figure 13.

'breaker trip': if the breaker is ready and detects a fault current through the VI, it automatically trips - this can also happen if the RCS is closed on a grid fault

'breaker busy': the breaker - as the client - sets the corresponding register of the control computer to a defined value

'breaker not busy': the breaker - as the client - sets the corresponding register of the control computer to a defined value different than that corresponding to 'breaker busy'

'fault occurred': the breaker - as the client - send a message to the control computer about the detected fault

'periodic comm. channel check': by a periodically attempting to write a specific register and by receiving the corresponding MODBUS response, the breaker can decide if the communication link with the computer is dead/alive at the moment

Consortium

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